

Residents' Awareness and Perception of Tourist Attractions in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

T. G. Yusuf

Abstract

The study assessed Ibadan residents' awareness and perception of tourist attractions. While four objectives were achieved by the study, two hypotheses were tested. An equal number of 20 respondents from each of the 11 local government areas within Ibadan metropolis were selected by simple random sampling technique, hence, 220 respondents participated in the survey. Structured questionnaire titled 'Residents' Awareness and Perception of Tourist Attractions in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria' was used to gather data from residents of Ibadan. The study identified both ancient (cultural festival, ancient palace, and monument) and modern (museum, amusement parks, zoological garden, and shopping malls) tourists' destinations in Ibadan. The study established that the residents were much more aware of the modern attractions than the ancient attractions. The study determined the residents' perception of tourist attractions and established the challenges of tourism in Ibadan to include lack of disposable income ($x = 1.82$), lack of government commitment to the development of the attractions ($x = 1.82$), lack of leisure time ($x = 1.61$), poor orientation of residents about tourism ($x = 1.57$), poor state of the attractions ($x = 1.56$) and absence of tour guide ($x = 1.54$). Correlation analysis showed a positive and significant relationship between age ($r = 0.252$), education ($r = 0.155$), cosmopolitanism ($r = 0.22$) and awareness of tourist attractions. Correlation analysis also showed a negative but significant relationship between age ($r = -0.038$) and perception of tourist attractions. There was also significant relationship between income ($r = 0.098$) and residents' perception of tourist attractions. The study concluded that orientation, re-orientation, and emphasis of the benefits of tourist's attraction is germane for better appreciation by the respondents. Improving the income derivable by the respondents will also boost their awareness and perception. The study recommended that; Oyo Stake Tourism Board in conjunction with; Nigeria Tourism Development Corporation, National Association of Tour Operators, Hotelier Association of Nigeria, and other relevant bodies should strive to sustainably develop, publicize, and market the destinations (particularly ancient attractions) and adequately orientate the residents about importance of tourism.

Key words: *Leisure, Perception, Attractions, Tourism, Sustainable Development*

Introduction

Tourism is crucial for the global economic development (World Tourism Organization, 2018), yet it is a very transversal industry that affects not only the economy of a destination but also its environment, its society, and its culture. Community perceptions and attitudes are crucial for successful and sustainable tourism development because an understanding of community's attitudes and perceptions and how these perceptions are formed regarding

tourism development would be valuable knowledge for decision makers. Host community is the most important party since they will be the most affected either positively or negatively by tourism planning and development. The factors which influence residents' perceptions and attitudes, as well as the nature and the impact of tourism are likely to be different in each community (Sajad, and Mahdi, 2012). Ijeoma and Okoli (2016) stated that the level of host

community's awareness of the ecodestinations as tourism sites rated high, but the participation was very low. According to Frauman and Banks(2011), tourism causes traffic and pedestrian congestion, parking problems, disturbance and destruction of flora and fauna, air and water pollution, and littering.

A sustainable tourism industry is predicated on several factors; in particular, consideration should be given to the impact that tourism has on the host community (Cahndralal, 2010). Tourism perceptions by residents of host community have gained academic attention during the last decades, and their importance for planning issues, in terms of sustainable development, has been acknowledged (Dyer, Gursoy, Sharma, and Carter, 2007). It has been recognized that the evaluation of residents' perceptions could be a valuable component in identifying and measuring tourism impacts (Getz, 1994); in fact, most tourism impact studies have been conducted through measuring residents' attitudes towards tourism and the effects that are perceived by community residents (Zhang, Inbakaran, and Jackson, 2006).

According to Ibimilua (2009), there is a significant relationship between residents' awareness and participation support for tourism. Butler (2006) claimed that there is a correlation between the development of tourism and the attitude of the residents towards the tourists. A destination must be known to its residents to make certain that they support tourism attractions and facilities that will build a sustainable tourism environment. Litheko and Potgieter (2016), established that residents of tourism destinations of Mahikeng, South Africa have poor knowledge and awareness of tourism facilities. While success in the tourism industry depends upon diverse attractions and quality services offered to tourists, it requires the hospitality and support of the residents and the community in general (Phoebe, 2013). While "host" communities are expected to offer a friendly welcome, this hospitality could be turned to hostility in some tourism destinations (Deery, Jago, and Fredline, 2012) which is rather distinguished

by unfriendly behaviors. For instance, in the city of Giroma in Spain, the city does not suffer from major conflicts between residents and tourism, notwithstanding some voices of concern were raised in the city showing discomfort with the tourism activities (Carreras and Pastells, 2017; Pastells, 2017). According to Juan, Marta, and Linda (2014), residents will be more inclined to support tourism programs if they perceive that tourism causes positive effects on the environment and when positive environmental effects exceed negative effects.

Residents perceiving tourism as a cause of increase in the level of investment at the destination and better public services will support policies aiming at the conservation of environmental and cultural resources. A step to address tourism aversion is to collect more information about the perception of residents towards the possibility of executing tourism activities, using the instrument of public discussions or workshops with experts. Since tourism relies heavily upon the goodwill of the residents, their support is essential for its development, successful operation, and sustainability of the industry in the long term (Vargas-Sánchez, Plaza-Mejia, and Porrás-Bueno, 2011; Brida, Osti, and Faccioli, 2011). Therefore, knowledge of residents' perceptions is relevant for both the well-being of the local communities (Andereck, Valentine, Vogt, and Knopf, 2007) and for the development of tourism in a sustainable manner (Deery *et. al.*, 2012). Kola, Idowu, Tinun, Olusola, Omotayo, and Oyeyemi, (2021) in a study done at Okomu National Park, Edo State, Nigeria, host communities were not fully aware of the value and essence of tourist attractions. The importance of understanding residents' perceptions of the impact of tourism is critical to the successful development of tourism as well as local support for tourism development (Látková and Vogt, 2012; Rasoolimanesh, Ringle, Jaafar, and Ramayah, 2017) and the satisfaction of host communities. (Xie, Bao, and Kerstetter, 2014; Ribeiro, Pinto, Silva, and Woosnam, 2017). Regrettably, despite such benefits to the

community, negative impact can occur when tourists interact with residents. For instance, tourism increases the cost of living and contributes to increase in crime, the use of drugs, both human and vehicular traffic, leading to a big change in the culture of residents as well as environmental damage (Latkovaet. *al.*, 2012). There is the need to understand residents' awareness and perception of tourists' attraction in Ibadan which is the largest city in Nigeria with numerous tourist attractions.

Objectives

The main objective of the study was to assess residents' awareness and perception of tourist attractions in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. identify the tourist attractions in Ibadan
- ii. determine residents' awareness of tourism attractions in Ibadan
- iii. determine residents' perception of tourists' attractions in Ibadan
- iv. identify the challenges of tourism in Ibadan.

Hypotheses: The hypotheses tested were the following.

- i. There is no significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and awareness of tourists' attractions.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and perception of tourists' attractions.

Methodology

Research Design: Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Data and result was generalizable to similar populations.

Study Area: The study was done in Ibadan, which is the capital city of Oyo State and the largest city in Nigeria by geographical area. It is the third most populated city in Nigeria after Lagos and Kano and covers

about 3,080 square kilometers. Its coordinates are 7.3775° N, 3.9470° E. Ibadan, an historical town, the seat of the old western region in Nigeria and the largest city in West Africa is blessed with many numerous tourism resources such as the national museum, historical structures (*Mapo Hall, Bowers' Memorial Tower and Irefin Palace*), modern attractions (amusement parks, hotels, cinemas, beautiful shopping malls and gardens), Zoology gardens, festivals (*Oke Ibadan and Egungun*). It houses the first television station in Africa (NTA, Ibadan), first skyscraper in Africa (Cocoa House), first Stadium in Africa (Liberty Stadium), and first University in Nigeria (University of Ibadan), first dual road in Nigeria (Queen Elizabeth Road), first teaching hospital in Nigeria (University College Hospital), first housing estate (Bodija Housing Estate), and first set of research and training institutes in Nigeria (the Forestry Research Institute (1930), the Idi-Ayunre Cocoa Research Institute (CRIN), the Nigerian Cereal Research Institute Moor Plantation (NCRI), the NIHORT (Nigerian Institute of Horticultural Research), the NISER (Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research), IAR&T (Institute of Agriculture, Research and Training)).

Population

The population of the study consists of the residents of all the eleven local government areas that make up Ibadan metropolis. There are over three million, six hundred and forty-nine (3,649,000) people in the state.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study area is made up of eleven local government areas. Since tourist attractions are scattered all over Ibadan city, all the local government areas were purposively selected for data collection. Residents of the location of tourist attraction were the target study population. Twenty respondents were selected by simple random sampling techniques from each of the eleven local government areas of the state, hence 220 respondents participated in the study and constituted the study sample.

Method of Data Collection

Structured Questionnaire was used to gather data. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. Reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. Four research assistants were involved in the data collection.

Data Analysis Technique:

The data collected were coded and entered the spread sheet of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The version 20 of SPSS was used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and mean were used to present the data. Mean (\bar{x}) values were used. four scale indices scored as; not aware (1), low awareness (2), moderate awareness (3), and high awareness (4) was adopted to measure respondents' level of awareness of the identified attractions. Thus, a mean score of 2.5 and above indicates moderate and high level of awareness and a mean score

below 2.5 indicates very low or no awareness. Percentage distribution was used to measure perception.

Results

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents' awareness of tourist attractions in Ibadan. The respondents showed three levels of awareness, not aware, low, medium and high as shown in the analysis: very much aware of the following attractions: Agodi Gardens ($\bar{x} = 2.80$), National Museum ($\bar{x} = 2.22$), Cocoa House ($\bar{x} = 2.65$), Ventura Mall ($\bar{x} = 2.55$), Jericho Mall ($\bar{x} = 2.65$), Heritage Mall ($\bar{x} = 2.41$), Palms Mall ($\bar{x} = 2.54$), Trans Amusement Park ($\bar{x} = 2.35$), University of Ibadan Zoological Garden ($\bar{x} = 2.33$), and Mapo Hall ($\bar{x} = 2.22$). However, the respondents' awareness of the following attractions was very low; *Egungun* festival ($\bar{x} = 1.58$), *Okebadan* festival ($\bar{x} = 1.54$), Bower's Memorial Tower ($\bar{x} = 1.53$), and *Irefin* Palace ($\bar{x} = 1.43$).

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Awareness of Tourism Attractions n=220

Tourist Attractions	Not aware	Low	Medium	High	Mean \pm SD
Bower's Memorial Tower	42 (19.1%)	76 (34.5%)	46 (20.9%)	56 (25.5%)	1.53 \pm 1.07
National Museum	04 (1.8%)	32 (14.5%)	32 (14.5%)	90 (40.9%)	2.22 \pm 0.76
Mapo Hall	04 (1.8%)	32 (14.5%)	94 (42.7%)	90 (40.9%)	2.22 \pm 0.76
Agodi Gardens	02 (0.9%)	04 (1.8%)	30 (13.6%)	184 (83.6%)	2.80 \pm 0.50
Trans Amusement Park	06 (2.7%)	18 (8.2%)	88 (40.0%)	108 (49.1%)	2.35 \pm 0.75
Cocoa House	02 (0.9%)	00 (0.0%)	70 (31.8%)	148 (67.3%)	2.65 \pm 0.53
Jericho Mall	02 (0.9%)	00 (0.0%)	70 (31.8%)	148 (67.3%)	2.65 \pm 0.53
Palms Shopping Mall	02 (0.9%)	14 (6.4%)	66 (30.0%)	138 (62.7%)	2.54 \pm 0.66
Heritage Mall	08 (3.6%)	10 (4.5%)	86 (39.1%)	116 (52.7%)	2.41 \pm 0.74
Ventura Mall	06 (2.7%)	10 (4.5%)	60 (27.3%)	144 (65.5%)	2.55 \pm 0.71
Irefin Palace	28 (12.7%)	110 (50.0%)	42 (19.1%)	40 (18.2%)	1.43 \pm 0.93
Okebadan Festival	24 (10.9%)	100 (45.5%)	48 (21.8%)	48 (21.8%)	1.54 \pm 0.95
UI Zoological Garden	06 (2.7%)	16 (9.3%)	98 (44.5%)	100 (45.5%)	2.33 \pm 0.95
Egungun Festival	26 (11.8%)	82 (37.3%)	70 (31.8%)	42 (19.1%)	1.58 \pm 0.93

Table 2 revealed that; majority of respondents (80%) agreed tourist attractions contribute significantly to health, majority (63.7%), gate fees are usually expensive, majority, 78.2% perceived that tourist attractions can be visited any time, 92.7% believed attractions can facilitate infrastructural development of the

immediate environment, 84.5% believed they can encourage people to live where they are located, 94.5% it can generate employment opportunities, and 94.5% believed it can improve the economic activities of the location. While there were just 10% more respondents who believed sites of tourist attractions are meant for

celebrations (42.7%) than those that disagreed (32.7%). 65.5% disagreed that tourist attractions are to be visited during the holiday alone. 57.3% states that it can

encourage crime, while 56.4% states that Okebadan festival was not against their religious belief.

Table 2: Respondents' Perception of Tourist Attractions

Perception of Attractions	SA	A	U	D	SD
	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)
Tourist attractions are to be visited during holidays only.	40 (18.2%)	30 (13.2%)	06 (2.7%)	40 (18.2%)	104 (47.3%)
They can contribute to healthy living.	44 (20.0%)	132 (60.0%)	24 (10.9%)	10 (4.5%)	10 (4.5%)
Gate fees are usually expensive.	58 (26.4%)	82 (37.3%)	18 (8.2%)	60 (27.3%)	02 (0.9%)
They can be visited anytime.	56 (25.5%)	116 (52.7%)	04 (1.8%)	20 (9.1%)	24 (10.9%)
Visiting some attractions such as <i>Okebadan</i> is against my religion doctrine.	48 (21.8%)	22 (10.0%)	26 (11.8%)	60 (27.3%)	64 (29.1%)
They can facilitate infrastructural development of their immediate environment.	74 (33.6%)	130 (59.1%)	10 (4.5%)	04 (1.8%)	02 (0.9%)
They can encourage people to live where they are located.	96 (43.6%)	90 (40.9%)	12 (5.5%)	18 (8.2%)	04 (1.8%)
They can improve the economic activities of their location.	110 (50.0%)	98 (44.5%)	00 (0.0%)	02 (0.9%)	10 (4.5%)
They encourage crime	42 (19.1%)	38 (17.3%)	14 (6.4%)	80 (36.4%)	46 (20.9%)
They can provide employment opportunities.	66 (30.0%)	142 (64.5%)	02 (0.9%)	08 (3.6%)	02 (0.9%)
They can cause congestion	46 (20.9%)	40 (18.2%)	36(16.4%)	80 (36.4%)	18 (8.2%)
They can increase environmental pollution	34 (15.5%)	62 (28.2%)	40 (18.2%)	62 (28.2%)	22 (10.0%)
Tourist attractions are meant to be used as venues for celebrations-birthdays, weddings, anniversaries	62 (28.2%)	32 (14.5%)	54 (24.5%)	52 (23.6%)	20 (9.1%)
They are meant for shooting videos by musicians, actors, and actresses	54 (24.5%)	24 (11.0%)	44 (20.0%)	76 (34.5%)	22 (10.0%)

Table 3 shows distribution of respondents by challenges of tourism in *Ibadan* includes, lack of disposable income ($x= 1.82$), lack of government commitment to the development of the attractions ($x= 1.82$), lack of leisure time ($x= 1.61$), poor orientation of residents about tourism ($x= 1.57$), poor state of the attractions

($x= 1.56$), and absence of tour guide ($x=1.54$). Poor awareness of tourist attractions ($x= 1.40$), preference for other attractions outside *Ibadan*($x= 1.48$), poor road network ($x= 1.45$), and insecurity ($x= 1.82$) were not significant challenges for tourism in *Ibadan*.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by Challenges of Tourism in Ibadan
n = 220

Challenges	Yes	No	Mean±SD
	F. (%)	F. (%)	
Poor orientation of residents about tourism	160 (72.7%)	60 (27.3%)	1.57±0.45
Lack of disposable income	190 (86.4%)	30 (13.6%)	1.82±0.34
Lack of leisure time	180 (71.8%)	40 (18.2%)	1.61±0.34
Poor awareness of tourism attractions	132 (60.0%)	88 (40.0%)	1.40±0.49
Poor state of the tourism attractions	118 (53.6%)	102 (46.4%)	1.56±0.50
Preference for other attractions outside Ibadan	114 (51.8%)	106 (48.2%)	1.48±0.50
Lack of government commitment to the development of tourism attractions	190 (86.4%)	30 (13.6%)	1.82±0.34
Absence of tour guides	100 (45.5%)	120 (54.5%)	1.54±0.50
Poor road network	120 (54.5%)	100 (45.5%)	1.45±0.50
Poor security	110 (50.0%)	110 (50.0%)	1.30±0.50

The correlation matrix in table 4 shows a positive and significant relationship between age ($r = 0.252$, $p = 0.008$), education ($r = 0.155$, $p = 0.014$), cosmopolitanism ($r = 0.220$, $p = 0.020$) and awareness of tourist attractions.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix Showing the Relationship Between the Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents and Awareness of Tourist Attractions

Variables	Correlation coefficient (r)	Coefficient of determination (r^2)	Level of Significance (p)
Age	0.252	0.0635	0.008*
Education	0.155	0.0240	0.014*
Level of Income	0.119	0.0142	0.212
Cosmopolitanism	0.220	0.0484	0.020*

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level

The correlation matrix in table 5 shows that age ($r = -0.038$, $p = 0.034$) negatively correlated with residents' perception of tourist attractions. Also, level of income ($r = 0.098$, $p = 0.000$) has a positive and significant relationship with residents' perception of tourists' attractions.

Table 5: Correlation matrix showing the relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and perception of tourism attractions

Variables	Correlation coefficient (r)	Coefficient of determination (r^2)	Level of Significance (p)
Age	-0.038	0.0014	0.034*
Education	0.052	0.0027	0.590
Level of Income	0.098	0.0096	0.000*
Cosmopolitanism	0.263	0.0692	0.354

*Correlation is significant at 0.05

Discussion

This study showed that majority of the residents of Ibadan are much more aware of modern attractions than ancient attractions

and this agrees with Destination Competitiveness Model proposed by Dwyer & Kim (2003). According to this model,

destination competitiveness is influenced by four determinants, namely, tourism resources, situational conditions, destination management, and demand conditions. Majority of the respondents had a good perception of tourism except that; they perceived that tourists' attractions were meant to be visited during celebrations alone. This study established that age, education and cosmopolitanism are significant socio-economic factors that determine host community' awareness of tourist attraction. This implies that, the higher the age, level of education, and cosmopolitanism of residents of host communities, the better the awareness of the attractions. Furthermore, the study showed that; income has a positive and significant effect on host community's perception of tourism attractions. This implies that as income increases, residents' perception of tourists' attractions improves. Income, particularly disposable income is a very important tool for participating in tourism, hence, it is not out of place if it significantly influences residents' perception of tourism attractions. Age also negatively correlated with residents' perception of tourist attractions. This implies that younger adults have better perceptions of attractions than the older adults.

Conclusion and Recommendations

To ensure holistic tourism development, there is need to repackage and reintroduce ancient attractions to the residents of Ibadan. Such efforts must not tamper with the originality of such attractions. The level of awareness of social, environmental, economic, and health benefits of tourism among the residents is sufficient. However, the state of the economy (high cost of living) in Ibadan and certainly in other parts of Nigeria is one of the significant factors influencing people's participation in tourism. Challenges of tourism in Ibadan include lack of disposable income, lack of government commitment to the development of the attractions, lack of leisure time, poor orientation of residents about tourism, poor state of the attractions, and absence of tour guide. In line with the findings of this study, the following

recommendations were made.

- i. The status of heritage tourism assets (*Irefin* palace, *Okebadan* festival, and *Egungun* festival) should be reviewed by government and improved to be positioned for sustainable tourism. Furthermore, the state government in collaboration with private investors and Non - Governmental Organizations should explore the untapped tourism assets in the state, particularly the ancient attractions, thereby diversifying the economic base of the state and the Nation.
- ii. The state ministry of tourism in collaboration with Nigeria Tourism Development Corporation should orientate the residents to dislodge opinions such as, destinations are meant for celebrations and shooting of videos and movies alone.
- iii. Tourism stakeholders should always ensure that qualified and professional tour guides are always available at tourist destinations. Fascinating presentation of attraction sites and spots by tour guides forms an integral part of tourists' experience.

References

- Andereck, K.L., Valentine, K.M., Vogt, C.A. & Knopf, R. C. (2007), A Cross-Cultural Analysis of Tourism and Quality of Life Perceptions, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 15; 483 - 502.
- Brida, J.G., Osti, L. & Faccioli, M. (2011). Residents' Perception and Attitudes Towards Tourism Impacts: A Case Study of the Small Rural Community of Folgaria, Italy. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 18 (3), 359 - 385.
- Butler, R.W. (2006). The Concept of a Tourist Area Life Cycle of Evolution: Implications for Management of Resources, In R. Butler (ed.), *The Tourism Area Life Cycle: Applications and Modifications*. (1st

- ed, pp13-26). Channel View Publications.
- Cahndralal, K., P., L. (2010). Impacts of Tourism and Community Attitude Towards Tourism: A Case Study in Sri Lanka. *South Asian Journal of Tourism and Heritage*, 3 (2); 41-49.
- Carreras, J. &Pastells, J. (2017). Residents' Perception of Tourism. Retrieved from www.ara.cat/comarquesgironines/volen-airbnb-nomes-ofereixi and accessed on 22/12/2020.
- Deery, M., Jago, L. &Fredline, L. (2012), Rethinking Social Impacts of Tourism Research: A New Research Agenda, *Tourism Management*, 33 (1); 64 - 73.
- Dwyer, L. & Kim, C. (2003). Destination Competitiveness: Determinants and Indicators. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 6(5); 369-414. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500308667962>.
- Dyer, P., Gursoy, D., Sharma, B. &Carter, J. (2007). Structural Modeling of Resident Perceptions of Tourism and Associated Development on the Sunshine Coast, Australia. *Tourism Management*, 28(2); 409-422. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2006.04.002>.
- Frauman, E. & Banks, S. (2011). Gateway Community Resident Perceptions of Tourism Development: Incorporating Importance Performance Analysis into a Limits of Acceptable Change Framework. *Tourism Management*, 32 (1); 128 - 140.
- Getz, D. (1994). Residents' Attitudes Towards Tourism: A Longitudinal Study in Spey Valley, Scotland. *Tourism Management*. 15(4); 247-258. Retrieved from [https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177\(94\)90041-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177(94)90041-8) and accessed on 22/12/2020.
- Ibimilua, A. F. (2009). Tourism Participation: Attractions, Influences and Key Trends in Ekiti State, Nigeria, *African Research Review*, 3(3); 244 - 258.
- Ijeoma, H. M. &Okoli, C.I. (2016). Assessment of Tourist Visitation and Host Communities' Participation in the Management of Selected Ecotourism Destinations in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Tourism and Hospitality*, 2 (1); 19 - 33.
- Kola, F.; Idowu, O.; Tinun, E.; Olusola, A.; Omotayo, S. & Oyeyemi, S. (2021). Level of Acceptability, General Perception and Views of Ecotourism to Local People around Okomu National Park, Nigeria. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality*, 5(2); 35 - 52
- Pastells, J. (2017) "Alert of Proliferation of Tourism Apartments in Girona, Spain. Retrieved from www.ara.cat/comarquesgironines/alertaproliferacioturistics and accessed on 11/ 12/2020
- Látková, P. & Vogt, C. (2012). Residents' Attitudes Toward Existing and Future Tourism Development in Rural Communities. *Journal of Travel Research*, 51; 50 - 67.
- Litheko, A. M. & Potgieter, M. (2016). Residents' Awareness and Support for Tourism in Mahikeng, South Africa, *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 5(2); 1-17.
- Rasoolimanesh, S.M.; Ringle, C.M.; Jaafar, M. &Ramayah, T. (2017). Urban Vs. Rural Destinations: Residents' Perceptions, Community Participation and Support for Tourism Development. *Tourism Management*, 60; 147 - 158.
- Ribeiro, M.A.; Pinto, P.; Silva, J.A. &Woosnam, K.M. (2017). Residents' Attitudes and The Adoption of Pro-Tourism Behaviours: The Case of Developing Island Countries. *Tourism Management*, 61; 523 - 537.
- Sajad A. E. & Mahdi, K. (2012). Community Perception of Tourism Impacts and their Participation in Tourism Planning: A Case Study of Ramras, Iran. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*;36: 333 - 341

- Vargas-Sánchez, A.; Plaza-Mejia, M.; & Porras-Bueno, N. (2011). Understanding Residents' Attitudes Toward the Development of Industrial Tourism in A Former Mining Community. *Journal of Travel Research*, 47; 373 - 387.
- World Travel and Tourism Council (2018). *Travel and Tourism Economic Impact 2018*, London.
- World Tourism Organization (2018), *UNWTO Tourism Highlights*, World Tourism Organization, Madrid.
- Xie, H.J.; Bao, J.; & Kerstetter, D.L. (2014). Examining the Effects of Tourism Impacts on Satisfaction with Tourism between Native and Non-Native Residents. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 16; 241 - 249.
- Zhang, J., Inbakaran, R. J. & Jackson, M. (2006). "Understanding Community Attitudes Towards Tourism and Host-Guest Interaction in the Urban-Rural Border Region", *Tourism Geographies*, 8(2); 182-204.